

SAVING ELECTRICAL ENERGY USING SIMPLE TECHNIQUES AT HOME

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Abstract

All of us use electricity at homes. There are number of positive aspects of energy saving associated with our daily energy saving habits. There are many ways you can use less electricity right now. Standby Power is an issue not well-known in India, however is becoming a huge problem. About 0.5 to 0.25 watts of electricity used by an appliance when it is on standby power. Standby Power not only wastes money, it has a large environmental impact. About 25% of the energy used by a television is used when the television is turned off. Data for the current study were collected at 'Shree Chhatrapati Shivaji High School, Jasai', a rural area from Uran, Dist- Raigad. Power consumption was measured by existing author using electronic energy meter. Awareness towards electricity saving in students was created by existing arranging a half day workshop. Switching to LED lighting can save 40% to 70% of the electricity. Today's energy efficient bulbs are available in the wide range of colours and light levels you've come to expect. While the initial price of energy efficient bulbs is typically higher than traditional incandescent light bulbs, newer bulbs cost less to operate, saving you money over the life of the bulb. Many of the newer bulbs last significantly longer than traditional bulbs, so you won't need to replace them as often. Using solar light also helps to save electrical energy at home.

Keywords: Electricity saving, Electronic energy meter, LED

Hypothesis:

With my current knowledge of the subject, I believe the most cost-effective switch is to replace standard incandescent light bulbs (SILs) with compact fluorescent light bulbs (CFLs). The second cost-effective switch will be switching regular appliances with energy star appliances. However, unplugging appliances when not in use will reduce energy consumption.

INTRODUCTION:

It's hard to imagine life without electricity. In our homes, we rely on it to power our lights, appliances and electronics. Many of us also use electricity to provide our homes with hot water, heat, and air conditioning. There are many ways you can use less electricity right now. In this research paper author tried to find simple ways to save electrical energy. With the help of electronic energy meter existing research is done by author. An 'electronic energy meter' is an electricity meter monitor that helps you monitor your kWh power consumption. Using information from an 'electronic energy meter', you can start to manage your kWh usage to save money. Use the product to educate your family about the costs so they too can save energy. Studies have shown that you can save 10% of your power bill simply by monitoring and understanding use.

Appliances and electronics that are turned "off" but still use electricity, can be called "leaking electricity". Standby Power is an issue not well-known in India, however is becoming a huge problem. About 0.5 to 0.25 watts of electricity used by an appliance when it is on standby power. Standby Power not only wastes money, it has a large environmental impact. About 25% of the energy used by a television is used when the television is turned off. Existing research helps student to save their electrical energy as well as money.

OBJECTIVES:

Objectives of the current study are-

1. To know awareness towards electricity saving among students.
2. To find the most cost-effective, electricity saving choices that can be implemented at home.

METHODOLOGY OF RESEARCH:

For this experiment I will use :

- A Pencil
- A Laptop/ Computer
- Paper
- Home Appliances
- Electronic Energy Meter
- Power Bills

Data for the current study were collected at ‘Shree Chhatrapati Shivaji High School, Jasai’, a rural area from Uran, Dist- Raigad. Study participants were drawn from Standard- 9th Division- E during the 2014-15 school year. All students were invited to participate. All students were participated from existing class. From this class 50 students agreed to participate.(Response rate 100%). These students were from 8 different villages.

Measures: 1

Power consumption was measured by existing author using electronic energy meter. Students noted electronic meter’s first reading on 01 December 2014 as R-1. This reading was noted by self-report using a laptop. Then second reading was noted on 08 December 2014 as R-2. Total power consumption was calculated by a formula $R2 - R1$ (difference between first and second reading) noted as T-2.

Then remaining measures were assessed by a questionnaire. Student’s knowledge about electricity saving was assessed with the question “Do you have any of these energy efficiency measures installed in your home?”

To know student’s general habits related to electricity consumption two questions were asked “Do you turn off lights when you leave a room?,” “Do you power off television When you are not watching?” with response option ‘Yes’ or ‘Not’.

With questions like “Can you name 2 ways you can save energy that would cost nothing?” student’s thinking towards the electricity saving was assessed. Few questions with behaviour at home related to electronic appliances were also asked.

Awareness: Awareness towards electricity saving in students was created by existing author arranging a half day workshop on 10 December 2014 at ‘Shree Chhatrapati Shivaji High School, Jasai’. In this workshop following instructions had been given to students:

- ✓ Change your incandescent light bulbs to light-emitting diode (LED) lights.
- ✓ Set your home’s thermostats a few degrees lower. For each one degree change, your family can save up to 5% on your home’s heating and cooling costs!
- ✓ Turn off lights and all electronics (like computers, televisions, stereos, and video-games) when you leave a room.
- ✓ Use microwave instead of the oven for cooking your meals.
- ✓ Use machines like washers, dryers after 8 p.m.
- ✓ Open your blinds or curtains on sunny days to let the sun shine into your home.

Saving Electricity Workshop for students (10 December 2014)

Measures: 2

After the workshop students tries to follow instructions given by author. Students noted electronic meter's third reading on 11 December 2014 as R-3. This reading was also noted by self-report using a laptop. Then fourth reading was noted on 18 December 2014 as R-4. Total power consumption before workshop was noted as T-2 calculating a formula $R2-R1$ (difference between first and second reading).

DATA ANALYSIS and INTERPRETATION:

All analysis was conducted using survey procedures to adjust for the clustered sample design.

The final study sample of student's habits towards electricity saving had a high prevalence of irresponsibleness. Detailed information on the students knowledge towards the electricity saving is reported.

In total of 36% of students having information about renewable source of energy.

(Chart 1)

In total of 8% of students never turn off lights when they leave room.

(Chart 2)

34% students never power off television when they are not watching.

(Chart 3)

Most of the students could not tell some ways of energy saving.

Total power unit consummated by 50 students from 01 December 2014 to 08 December 2014 (8 Days) were 2616 Units(T-1).

After workshop about awareness towards energy saving the average power unit consummated in next 8 days from 11 December 2014 to 18 December 2014 were 2453 Units(T-2).

(Chart 4)

CONCLUSION:

Our findings suggest that there are number of positive aspects of energy saving associated with our daily energy saving habits.

Using solar light instead of power bulb can save much more electricity.

We can save money on our power bills by changing from incandescent light bulbs to light-emitting diode (LED) lights.

Turning off electronic equipments instead of putting them on standby mode also can save electricity.

SCOPE FOR FUTURE WORK:

Using information from the An ‘electronic energy meter’, you can start to manage your kWh usage to save money. Use the product to educate your family about the costs so they too can save energy. Studies have shown that you can save 10% of your power bill simply by monitoring and understanding use.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT:

- Rayat Shikshan Sanstha, Satara
- Homi Bhabha Centre for Science Education
- Dr.Ganesh Thakur (Secretary,Rayat Shikshan Sanstha, Satara)
- Dr. Anil Palve (Asst. Prof. MPASC College, Panvel)
- Mr.Patil S.B. (Head Master, SCS High. Jasai)

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Questionnaire

I am **Mr. Tushar Chandrakant Mhatre**, assistant teacher at Rayat Shikshan Sanstha's **Shri Chhatrapati Shivaji High school and Loknete D. B. Patil junior College Jasai**. I am conducting a questionnaire to find out about energy consumption in our homes as part of my research paper on electricity saving. If you could take a few minutes to complete the questionnaire we would be very grateful. Thank you for your time.

Name: Address:

1. Which of these is a renewable source of energy?
A. Coal B. Sun C. Oil D. Natural Gas
2. How long do you shower for?
A. Less than 3 minutes B. Less than 5 minutes
C. Less than 10 minutes D. More than 10 minutes
3. Do you have any of these energy efficiency measures installed in your home?
A. Insulation – loft, cavity walls, floors, etc. B. Draught-proofing of the windows and doors
C. Use of low voltage lamps D. Insulation of the hot water cylinder
Other: _____
4. Do you turn off lights when you leave a room?
A. Yes B. No
5. Do you put on the washing machine when it's not full?
A. Yes B. No
6. Do you power off T.V. when you are not watching?
A. Yes B. No
7. Do you fill the kettle when you only want one cup of tea?
A. Yes B. No
8. Can you name 2 ways you can save energy that would cost nothing?
A. _____
B. _____
9. Have you ever heard of the Solar Energy?
A. Yes B. No
10. What do you think would be a good incentive to people to be more active in saving energy?

ANNEXURES:

POWER CONSUMPTION IN EXPERIMENTED PERIOD

Sr No.	Student Name	Address	1st Reading (R-1)	2nd Reading (R-2)	Total power consumed T1 = (R1 - R2)	3rd Reading (R-3)	4th Reading (R-4)	Total power consumed T2 = (R3 - R4)	Total Difference (T1 - T2)
1	Paikarao Jaypal Datta	Jasai	1452	1486	34	1488	1512	24	10
2	Raut Gautam Bharat	Jasai	3214	3272	58	3276	3329	53	5
3	Gharat Manthan Dhondur	Chirle	2109	2152	43	2159	2201	42	1
4	Gharat Jitendra Vilas	Jasai	946	968	22	974	998	24	-2

5	Madhavi Hritik Namdev	Chirle	1861	1917	56	1920	1969	49	7
6	Mhatre Saurav Ashok	Surungpa da	779	790	11	791	801	10	1
7	Panchal Hritik Ramesh	Chirle	1023	1048	25	1053	1075	22	3
8	Patil Rutikesh Hiraji	Chirle	2786	2889	103	2898	2996	98	5
9	Thakur Nihal Ram	Dhutum	5717	5852	135	5859	5985	126	9
10	Thakur Pratik Namdev	Dhutum	10839	10897	58	10906	10963	57	1
11	Thakur Shubham Sanjay	Dhutum	6577	6683	106	6691	6793	102	4
12	Thakur Swastik Pralhad	Dhutum	9103	9183	80	9191	9265	74	6
13	Thakur Kalpesh Shantaram	Chirle	6447	6476	29	6478	6500	22	7
14	Badadal Shivappa Jatappa	Jasai	852	873	21	879	900	21	0
15	Bhosale Atish Vijay	Jasai	1325	1359	34	1365	1395	30	4
16	Dalavi Avinash Maruti	Chirle	2867	2888	21	2896	2915	19	2
17	Hambir Mahesh Dasharath	Shirke	1123	1149	26	1154	1179	25	1
18	Kadam Kunal Kashiram	Chirle	1336	1371	35	1378	1411	33	2
19	Khan Rahiman Akabar	Jasai	1247	1275	28	1281	1309	28	0
20	Nikam Akshay Balakrush	Jasai	993	1025	32	1029	1059	30	2
21	Rajput Suraj Hanuman	Jasai	4306	4345	39	4353	4389	36	3
22	Shrivastav Anamol Saroj	Jasai	3261	3288	27	3294	3319	25	2
23	Shrivastav Sachin Vikas	Jasai	5812	5841	29	5848	5875	27	2
24	Bhalekar Sumit Suraj	Jasai	1349	1381	32	1385	1415	30	2
25	Lavate Anil Appa	Jasai	4924	4958	34	4961	4992	31	3
26	Mhatre Rohit Sanjay	Jasai	18474	18538	64	18545	18607	62	2
27	Patil Rushikesh Uday	Ranjanpa da	13586	13659	73	13667	13739	72	1
28	Patil Jay Sanjay	Ranjanpa da	1584	1621	37	1630	1664	34	3
29	Patil Nivas Subhash	Chirle	2867	2888	21	2896	2915	19	2

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30	Thakur Hritik Nirdosh	Dhutum	8718	8758	40	8769	8806	37	3
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POWER CONSUMPTION IN EXPERIMENTED PERIOD

Sr · No ·	Student Name	Address	1st Readi ng (R-1)	2nd Readi ng (R-2)	Total power consum ed T1 = (R1 - R2)	3rd Readi ng (R-3)	4th Readi ng (R-4)	Total power consum ed T2 = (R3 - R4)	Total Differen ce (T1 - T2)
31	Patil Pooja Chandramani	Jasai	14129	14263	134	14272	14399	127	7
32	Podamal Tai Shraavan	Shirke	1253	1271	18	1279	1301	22	-4
33	Khatake Ekanksha Bala	Jasai	3818	3846	28	3851	3877	26	2
34	Khatake Geeta Vitthal	Jasai	3615	3648	33	3654	3685	31	2
35	Palekar Sonal Anil	Belpada	2137	2329	192	2338	2524	186	6
36	Gharat Apurva Dhanaji	Jasai	10099	10182	83	10190	10270	80	3
37	Gharat Apeksha Jeevan	Jasai	2210	2302	92	2312	2403	91	1
38	Mumbaikar Priyanka Gaja	Veshvi	2316	2377	61	2389	2447	58	3
39	Mumbaikar Vrushali Raj	Veshvi	1856	1905	49	1913	1960	47	2
40	Mhatre Amisha Padaji	Belpada	7582	7625	43	7633	7671	38	5
41	Mhatre Khushaboo Dnyan	Belpada	4128	4158	30	4167	4193	26	4
42	Mhatre Rani Dnyaneshwar	Belpada	4128	4158	30	4167	4193	26	4
43	Patil Ankita Avinash	Chirle	5269	5314	45	5323	5364	41	4
44	Patil Asmita Laxman	Chirle	2908	3011	103	3019	3123	104	-1
45	Patil Kalyani Suresh	Chirle	5623	5676	53	5684	5731	47	6
46	Patil Monika Lahoo	Chirle	1026	1061	35	1063	1094	31	4
47	Patil Pooja Gajanan	Chirle	10058	10130	72	10143	10204	61	11
48	Patil Swati Sanjay	Veshvi	3582	3656	74	3664	3732	68	6
49	Patil Vinaya Rohidas	Veshvi	1242	1271	29	1278	1308	30	-1
50	Yelakar Sejal Vijay	Chirle	13852	13911	59	13920	13971	51	8
			Total		2616	Total		2453	163